

The Chemistry of Furan Derivatives. V. Reaction of Ethyl Cyanoacetate with Furfural Anils

J. S. Sandhu, Suresh Mohan and P. S. Sethi

The furan derivatives are being extensively studied due to their interesting reactions with electrophilic and nucleophilic reagents¹. The furfural aldehyde has been the subject of a few investigation where it could be established to be true aromatic aldehyde, undergoing benzoin and Cannizzaro's type of reactions². The anils of this aldehyde have attracted little attention, only recently a convenient route to their preparation and nucleophilic addition of cyanide ion has been described³. The present communication deals with the addition of ethylcyanoacetate on furfuralanils.

The furfurylidene-arylamines I were prepared by mixing equimolar quantities of furfural and appropriate amine as described earlier³. The equimolar quantities of furfurylidene aniline (0.01 mol) and ethylcyanoacetate (0.01 mol) were allowed to react in dry benzene at room temperature for 24 hrs. The evaporation of the solvent, and recrystallisation of the residue from petroleum ether gave white crystalline compound, C₁₀H₉NO₃, m.p. 94° (80% yield). (Found : % of C, 62.72, H, 4.54; N, 7.28, mol. wt. 191. Calc.: % of C, 62.82; H, 4.71; N, 7.37, mol. wt. 191). The i.r. spectrum indicated C≡N at 2250 cm⁻¹ (w), and no N-H stretching frequency around 3300 cm⁻¹ indicating the compound to have structure III.

1. Advances in heterocyclic chemistry, Vol. VII, pp. 377, Ed. 1967.
2. J. S. Sandhu and Suresh Mohan *J. Indian Chem. Soc.* (In Press).
3. J. S. Sandhu, Suresh Mohan and P. S. Sethi, *Chem. and Ind.*, London (In Press).

This was confirmed by comparison with an authentic sample of furfurylidene ethylcyanoacetate (m.m.p.) obtained through Knoevengel condensation of furfural and ethylcyanoacetate catalysed by piperidine in dioxane at 8°. The same compound III was obtained in almost same yield when other imines having various substituents in the aniline were used.

The compound III could be the result of addition followed by elimination of basic part as mechanistically indicated above. It is interesting to note, under the conditions used by the authors for this condensation, the furan ring remained intact⁴.

Authors are thankful to Dr. S. C. Pakrashi of I.I.E.M., Calcutta for recording i.r. spectrum and Punjabi University, Patiala for financial assistance.

Department of Chemistry,
Punjabi University,
Patiala.

Received April 19, 1971

4. H. Yasuda, T. Hayashi and H. Midorikowa, *J. Org. Chem.*, 1970, **35**, 1234.